

MEANS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AND SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF CADETS

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Abstract: *A teaching tool is a timely link between a textbook and a teacher. Along with methods and organizational forms, they contribute to the successful implementation of learning goals.*

Keywords: *modern, cadets, training.*

In the conditions of modern socio-economic and political transformations, political integration and, accordingly, the increasing importance of strengthening the country's defense capability, the professional training of cadets of military universities involves ensuring the proper level of readiness to carry out professional activities. This readiness at the present stage of the development of the military education system is ensured by the achievement of mastering the necessary professional competencies, among which the cadet's communicative competence becomes a means of effective preparation for professional activity, as well as the goal of achieving successful initial professional self-realization.

The high level of speech culture of the future military is recognized today as an obligatory component. It includes an extensive vocabulary, in which a sufficient amount of specialized vocabulary is active, constantly being formed and meeting the requirements of stylistic, morphological, orthoepic, phonational, pronouncational norms of the Russian language. In this regard, teaching the mastery of properly formed oral speech becomes one of the most important tasks of teachers of the Russian language in a military educational institution.

At the present stage of the development of the military-professional field, the official activity of the military expands the boundaries of the impact of professionally-oriented oral speech, which is expressed in an increase in the variety of conversation styles; various kinds of presentations requiring verbal accompaniment; negotiations carried out in different modes: from planned to situational with a given time limit; telephone conversations, clear commands, explanations requiring not only a clear expression of thought, but also correct diction, the tone of phrase construction,

taking into account the norms and rules of the Russian language, as well as all kinds of interviews, debates, etc.

Modern public speech is a complex stylistic unity and most clearly reflects the state of the speech culture of society as a whole. Describing the public speech of the recent past, its monotony and official nature were most often noted. More than one generation of cadets was brought up under the influence of speech patterns from speeches read out on paper. The change in speech practice over the past decades and the shift of cultural and ethical values in society necessitate the development and justification of scientific and pedagogical foundations for the formation of the speech culture of cadets. Russian Russian language teaching problem of future fitzers as an educational and educational task of training specialists who think freely and know the traditions of Russian speech culture has not been sufficiently investigated. At the same time, it must be recognized that a lot has been done in scientific, theoretical and practical terms to form the speech culture of society as a whole.

This situation imposes requirements on the teacher of the Russian language and on the content of the discipline itself, which predetermine taking into account the versatility of the formation of language competence, the essential structural and component elements of which is orthoepic competence.

Currently, the problems of the formation of orthoepic competence in the framework of teaching the discipline "Russian language" at the stage of initial professional self-realization are widely discussed in modern scientific and specialized literature. For example, the speech culture of university cadets and its role in professional training is given quite serious attention in the works of E. F. Smooth, N. P. Tyumeneva, S. A. Prokhotskaya, etc. Formation of competencies within the framework of teaching the discipline "Russian language" (including orthoepic competence) is studied in the works of A. I. Mikhantseva, E. V. Mishurova, O. Z. Titova, etc. [3; 5; 6]. Increasing the importance of the correctness of the use of oral speech in a professional context indicates the need for the formation of the orthoepic competence of future specialists (including military personnel).

The methodology of the formation of the students' orthoepic competence, from our point of view, should include: -synthesis of new knowledge, including analysis of information in Russian obtained from

sources of artistic, scientific, journalistic material, as well as mass media; such analysis anticipates the formation of speech culture by attracting new knowledge; Russian Russian - expanding horizons at the expense of knowledge about the Russian language itself in the field of orthoepy (for example, knowledge about the existence of the melodics of the Russian language – silver, gold, velvet, copper tones – can enrich the speech culture of cadets with samples of intonation-melodic expression, in which, in one case, grace or efficiency will be traced, in the other, spirituality, speed, musicality, etc.; the sound of Russian speech has formed into a unique melodic system, which in the process of oral speech can be placed in certain speech spaces, in connection with the

LITERATURE:

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